

Static Analysis and Family-based Model Checking of Featured Transition Systems with VMC

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ABSTRACT

A Featured Transition System (FTS) is a formalism for modelling variability in configurable systems, such as software product lines. The behaviour of all variants (products) is modelled in a single compact FTS by associating the possibility to perform an action and transition from one state to another with features that condition the execution of an action in specific variants. We present a front-end tool for the Variability Model Checker VMC such that the resulting toolchain allows a modeller to analyse an FTS for ambiguities (dead or false optional transitions and hidden deadlock states), transform an ambiguous FTS into an unambiguous one, and perform an efficient kind of family-based model checking of an FTS without hidden deadlock states. We use examples from the literature to illustrate the novelties offered by the toolchain.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Software and its engineering** → **Software product lines; Formal methods; Model checking; Automated static analysis.**

KEYWORDS

VMC, tool support, configurable systems, software product lines, variability models, featured transition systems, modal transition systems, static analysis, model checking

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1 INTRODUCTION

The automated analysis of variability models, such as the detection of anomalies like dead or false optional features in feature diagrams, has a 30-year history [16, 62]. Variability in behavioural models has a shorter history [3, 4, 44–48, 52, 54]. Moreover, such behavioural models received considerable attention only during the last decade, following the seminal paper by Classen et al. [27] that introduced FTSs and an efficient means to model check them.

An FTS is a formal model with variability encoding to capture the behaviour of all variants of a configurable system in a single transition system [26, 29]; its transitions, labelled with actions, are

associated with features that condition their presence in classical Labelled Transition Systems (LTSs) that model individual variant behaviour. Proving correctness of such behavioural models through model checking or testing is challenging. Ideally, the compactness of the FTS is exploited to reason on the whole system at once. Such an *all-in-one* technique, by which the behaviour of all variants is examined only once simultaneously, is called family-based analysis, in contrast to an enumerative product-based analysis, by which the behaviour of each individual variant is examined *one-by-one* [61]. During the past decade, FTSs proved amenable to family-based model-checking and testing [10, 15, 24–26, 28, 34, 35, 37, 38, 41, 50].

In [7, 9], we tackled the automated analysis of FTSs. We defined three ambiguities for an FTS: (i) a *dead transition* (i.e., a transition that is unreachable, and thus cannot be executed, in any variant); (ii) a *false optional transition* (i.e., a transition that can be executed in all variants in which its source state is reachable); and (iii) a *hidden deadlock state* (i.e., a state from which a transition can be executed only in some variants, but not all). In analogy with the above mentioned anomaly detection for variability models, we developed an algorithm to detect ambiguities in FTSs, and a means to resolve them, with a proof of its correctness. The motivations were twofold. First, an ambiguous FTS is often undesired, since it gives an unclear view of the behaviour of the configurable system. Second, an unambiguous FTS paves the way for an efficient kind of family-based model checking. We implemented this algorithm exploiting the SAT solving features of the Z3 SMT solver [32]. The Python code of our implementation (`analyser.py`), which accepts FTSs in the format `.dot` as input, is publicly available [8].

In this paper, we present FTS4VMC, a front-end for VMC [11, 13, 14], developed to make VMC amenable to FTSs. VMC¹ is a tool for the analysis of behavioural models with variability. It accepts as input a Modal Transition System (MTS) with a set of logical variability constraints (akin to an FTS' feature expressions). An MTS [51, 53] is an LTS that distinguishes admissible ('may'), necessary ('must'), and optional (may but not must) transitions which are such that by definition all necessary and optional transitions are also admissible. VMC offers explicit-state on-the-fly model checking of properties of MTSs expressed in the dedicated variability-aware action-based and state-based branching-time temporal logic *v*-ACTL [5, 11] derived from ACTL [33], which is an action-based version of the well-known logic CTL [21]. VMC offers both product-based analysis, upon explicit generation of behavioural variant models (LTSs), and a kind of family-based analysis (on MTSs). The latter relies on the fact that for properties expressed in *v*-ACTL^{live}[□], which

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¹<http://fmt.isti.cnr.it/vmc>

is a rich fragment of v-ACTL interpreted on so-called live MTSs, validity on the (live) MTS guarantees validity of the property for all its products (cf. [11, Theorem 4]).

FTS4VMC allows a modeller to check an FTS for ambiguities (dead or false optional transitions and hidden deadlock states), by calling `analyser.py`; to remove ambiguities and thus turn an ambiguous FTS into an unambiguous one, by calling `disambiguator.py`; to transform an FTS into an MTS, by calling `translator.py`; and to perform an efficient kind of family-based model checking of an MTS obtained in this way from an FTS without hidden deadlock states, by calling VMC via `vmc_controller.py`. The FTS4VMC implementation, including the Python code of `disambiguator.py` and `translator.py`, is publicly available from <https://github.com/fts4vmc/FTS4VMC>. We use examples from the literature to illustrate the novelties offered by this toolchain.

Outline. This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 discusses related work. The necessary background for understanding the paper is provided in Section 3. The toolchain is presented and applied to examples from the literature in Section 4. Section 5 anticipates future work, while Section 6 wraps up the paper.

2 RELATED WORK

An encompassing overview of analysis strategies for Software Product Lines (SPLs), including static analysis and model checking, can be found in [61] and a recent empirical study on applying variability-aware static analysis techniques to real-world configurable systems is presented in [59]. As anticipated, static analysis of FTSs mimics the automated analysis of variability models by defining behavioural counterparts of dead and false optional features [16, 62]. Furthermore, it is related to static (program) analysis [19, 57], such as bug detection in code (e.g., using a variable before its initialisation) but also the identification redundant or unreachable code.

Family-based model checking of behavioural variability models provides a means to simultaneously verify multiple behavioural variant models in a single run. Properties can be verified with dedicated SPL model-checking tools like SNIP [24, 26], ProVeLines [28], VMC [11, 13, 14], fNuSMV [25, 40], ProFeat [20] (for probabilistic model checking), or QFLan [12, 63] (for statistical model checking), or—through suitable abstractions or encodings—with well-known classical model checkers like SPIN [38, 39, 41], PRISM [43] (for probabilistic model checking), Maude [55], mCRL2 [10, 15], or NuSMV [37]. The aforementioned survey [61] also discusses software model checking, operating directly on source code in Java or C [2, 60].

3 BACKGROUND

LTSs are the underlying behavioural structure of MTSs and FTSs.

Definition 3.1 (LTS). A *Labelled Transition System (LTS)* is a quadruple $\mathcal{L} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta)$, where S is a finite (non-empty) set of states, Σ is a set of actions, $s_0 \in S$ is an initial state, and $\delta \subseteq S \times \Sigma \times S$ is a transition relation. We call $(s, a, s') \in \delta$ an a -(labelled) transition, which we may write as $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$.

We recall some classical notions for LTSs.

Definition 3.2 (path, reachability, deadlock). Let $\mathcal{L} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta)$ be an LTS. A sequence $p = s_0 t_1 s_1 t_2 s_2 \dots$ is a *path* of \mathcal{L} if $t_i =$

Figure 1: LTSs \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 modelling coffee machines

$(s_{i-1}, a_i, s_i) \in \delta$ for all $i > 0$; p is said to *visit* states s_0, s_1, \dots and transitions t_1, t_2, \dots and we denote its i th state by $p(i)$ and its i th transition by $p\{i\}$.

A state $s \in S$ is *reachable* (via p) in \mathcal{L} if there exists a path p that visits it, i.e., $p(i) = s$ for some $i \geq 0$; s is a *deadlock* if it has no outgoing transitions, i.e., $\nexists (s, a, s') \in \delta$, for all $a \in \Sigma$ and $s' \in S$.

A transition $t = (s, a, s') \in \delta$ is *reachable* (via p) in \mathcal{L} if there exists a path p that visits it, i.e., $p\{i\} = t$, for some $i > 0$.

Example 3.3. In Figure 1, we depict the LTSs \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 , modelling the behaviour of two different coffee machines, adapted from [7, 9, 10, 15]. Each LTS has actions to insert coins (*ins*) and to pour either standard (*std*) or extra large (*xxl*) coffee upon the insertion of one or two coins, respectively. Clearly all states are reachable and there are no deadlocks.

3.1 Featured Transition Systems

FTSs were introduced in [27] to concisely model the behaviour of all products of an SPL, modelled as LTSs, in one transition system by annotating transitions with conditions expressing their presence in (product) LTSs. Let $\mathbb{B} = \{\top, \perp\}$ denote the Boolean constants true (\top) and false (\perp), and let $\mathbb{B}(F)$ denote the set of propositional formulas over a set of features F (i.e., using features as propositional variables). The elements of $\mathbb{B}(F)$ are also called *feature expressions*. An FTS is an LTS equipped with a feature model and a function that labels each transition with a feature expression. In below definition, the feature model is represented by the set of its (variant) configurations, where each configuration is represented by a Boolean assignment to the features (i.e., selected = \top and unselected = \perp).

Definition 3.4 (FTS). A *Featured Transition System (FTS)* is a sextuple $\mathcal{F} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta, F, \Lambda)$, where S is a finite (non-empty) set of states, Σ is a set of actions, $s_0 \in S$ is the initial state, $\delta \subseteq S \times \Sigma \times \mathbb{B}(F) \times S$ is a transition relation, F is a set of features, and $\Lambda \subseteq \{\lambda : F \rightarrow \mathbb{B}\}$ is a set of (variant) configurations. Given a feature expression $\phi \in \mathbb{B}(F)$, $(s, a, \phi, s') \in \delta$ is called a *featured transition* (labelled with a and limited to configurations satisfying ϕ), which we may write as $s \xrightarrow{a|\phi} s'$, and $(s, a, \top, s') \in \delta$ *must transition*.

The notions from Definition 3.2 (path, reachability, deadlock) are carried over to FTSs by ignoring the feature expressions.

A configuration $\lambda \in \Lambda$ satisfies a feature expression $\phi \in \mathbb{B}(F)$, denoted by $\lambda \models \phi$, whenever ϕ is valid in the interpretation λ , i.e., the result of substituting the value of the features occurring as variables in ϕ according to λ is \top . Thus, by definition, $\lambda \models \top$.

Figure 2: FTS \mathcal{F} modelling a product line of coffee machines

Figure 3: Feature model of product line of coffee machines

Without loss of generality, in the sequel we only consider FTSs that do not contain two featured transitions $q \xrightarrow{a|\phi} q'$ and $q \xrightarrow{a|\phi'} q'$ such that $\phi \neq \phi'$. Any FTS that does not satisfy this criterion can be transformed into one that does by replacing the two transitions with one featured transition $q \xrightarrow{a|\phi \vee \phi'} q'$.

Definition 3.5 (variant of FTS). Let $\mathcal{F} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta, F, \Lambda)$ be an FTS. The LTS specified by a particular configuration $\lambda \in \Lambda$, denoted by $\mathcal{F}|_\lambda$, is called a *variant* (product) of \mathcal{F} . It is obtained from \mathcal{F} by first removing all featured transitions whose feature expressions are not satisfied by λ (resulting in the LTS $(S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta')$, with $\delta' = \{(s, a, s') \mid (s, a, \phi, s') \in \delta \text{ and } \lambda \models \phi\}$), and then removing all unreachable states and their outgoing transitions. Given a featured transition $(s, a, \phi, s') \in \delta$, we call $(s, a, s') \in \delta'$ its *corresponding (LTS) transition*. The set of variants of \mathcal{F} is denoted by $\text{lts}(\mathcal{F})$.

Note that, by construction: (i) no variant contains unreachable states or transitions, (ii) no variant contains states or actions that were not originally present in the FTS, (iii) each must transition of the FTS has a corresponding transition in the variants in which it is reachable, and (iv) each featured transition has a unique corresponding LTS transition when its source state is reachable.

The *feature (model) expression* of \mathcal{F} , denoted by $\text{FM}_{\mathcal{F}}$, is a feature expression representing Λ , i.e. for all $\lambda : F \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$, $\lambda \models \text{FM}_{\mathcal{F}}$ iff $\lambda \in \Lambda$.

Example 3.6. In Figure 2, we depict an FTS \mathcal{F} modelling the behaviour of the two coffee machines from Example 3.3 as a product line of coffee machines, adapted from [7, 9, 10, 15]. Imagine that extra large coffee is exclusively available for the American market, while standard coffee is exclusively available for the European market. Thus, \mathcal{F} has transitions labelled with features $\$$ and € , representing variants for either the American or the European market, respectively. Its feature model, depicted in Figure 3(left), can be represented by the feature expression $\text{FM}_{\mathcal{F}} = \$ \oplus \text{€}$, where \oplus denotes the *exclusive disjunction* operation. Hence the configurations of \mathcal{F} are $\Lambda = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2\}$, where $\lambda_1(\$) = \perp$, $\lambda_1(\text{€}) = \top$, $\lambda_2(\$) = \top$, and $\lambda_2(\text{€}) = \perp$. The LTSs $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_1} = \mathcal{L}_1$ and $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_2} = \mathcal{L}_2$, depicted in Figure 1, model the behaviour of the only two variants of \mathcal{F} : configuration λ_1 for the European and λ_2 for the American market.

3.2 Anomaly Detection in FTSs

When applying automated analysis of feature models, the better known analysis operations that are typically being performed concern the detection of anomalies (cf., e.g., [16, 62]). These anomalies reflect ambiguous or even contradictory information, such as dead and false optional features. A feature is *dead* if it is not contained in any configuration of the FTS, whereas it is *false optional* if it is contained in all configurations of the FTS even though it is not a designated mandatory feature. Such anomalies are typically due to an incorrect use of cross-tree constraints.

In [7, 9], we formalised equivalent notions in a behavioural setting, by adapting these well-known notions to (featured) transitions of an FTS. Recall from Definition 3.5 that all states of a (variant) LTS of an FTS are reachable from the initial state.

Definition 3.7 (dead transition [9]). We say that a transition (of an FTS) is *dead* to mean that in all the FTS's variants the corresponding (LTS) transition is not reachable.

Clearly, since an FTS is intended to compactly represent the behaviour of all variants of a product line, a dead transition in an FTS indicates a modelling error that must be signalled to the modeller so it can be corrected. Such correction can mean removing the transition or changing its feature expression.

Definition 3.8 (false optional transition [9]). We say that a transition (of an FTS) is *false optional* to mean that: (i) it is not dead, (ii) it is not annotated with the feature expression \top , and (iii) its corresponding (LTS) transition is present in all the FTS's variants in which its source state is present.

Definition 3.8 is a slightly revised version of that of [7, Def. 3.2], in which condition (i) was not explicitly required.

A false optional transition in an FTS indicates a redundancy, in the sense that the associated feature expression can be replaced by \top without changing the behaviour of any of the variants of the product line. This redundancy may be intentional syntactic sugar, to underline the fact that the considered transition is part of the behaviour of those configurations that satisfy the feature expression, but otherwise it may be useful for the modeller to know. Moreover, substitution of the feature expression with \top allows for more efficient verification because it results in one more must transition, and thus one less feature expression to be evaluated.

Example 3.9. In Figure 4, we depict an FTS \mathcal{F} with features f_1 and f_2 and feature expression $\text{FM}_{\mathcal{F}} = f_1 \oplus f_2$. The LTSs $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_1}$ and $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_2}$, also depicted in Figure 4, model the behaviour of its two valid configurations: $\lambda_1 = \{f_1\}$ and $\lambda_2 = \{f_2\}$. Note that transition $s_2 \xrightarrow{a|f_2} s_2$ is dead and transition $s_1 \xrightarrow{a|f_1} s_2$ is false optional.

An important safety property of systems concerns *deadlock freedom*, i.e., the system should not reach a state in which no further action is possible, thus guaranteeing progress or liveness [1, 56]. In case of configurable systems (like FTSs) this notion can be extended to guaranteeing liveness for each variant (LTS). Recall that a state of an FTS is said to be a deadlock if it has no outgoing transitions.

Definition 3.10 (hidden deadlock state [9]). We say that a state (of an FTS) is a *hidden deadlock* to mean that: (i) it is not a deadlock in the FTS, whereas (ii) it is a deadlock in at least one of the FTS's variants (LTSs).

Figure 4: FTS \mathcal{F} and its variant LTSs $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_1}$ and $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_2}$

Note that condition (ii) implies that hidden deadlock states of an FTS are present in one or more of its (variant) LTSs.

A hidden deadlock in the FTS should definitely be signalled to the modeller, so it can be checked whether the deadlocks in the LTSs should be remedied. If they should not, i.e., if the deadlocks in the LTSs are intended or unavoidable, then this should be made explicit in the FTS to improve understanding. Furthermore, as was shown in [7, 9], removing them enables a kind of family-based verification.

Definition 3.11 (ambiguous FTS). We say that an FTS is *ambiguous* to mean that: (i) at least one of its states is a hidden deadlock, or (ii) at least one of its transitions is dead or false optional.

Example 3.12. It is easy to see that state s_2 of the FTS \mathcal{F} depicted in Figure 4 is a hidden deadlock state, because s_2 is a deadlock in the LTS $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_1}$. Indeed, \mathcal{F} is an ambiguous FTS (cf. also Example 3.9).

In [7, 9], we showed how to resolve ambiguities in an FTS. A dead transition can be removed. However, this might not always be the right thing to do, since the modeller may simply have made a mistake in the behavioural model or in the feature model. Likewise for a false optional transition, which however might also be intentional, to make explicit that the (corresponding) transition is part of the behaviour of those configurations that satisfy the associated feature expression. Finally, a hidden deadlock should either be made explicit in the FTS, by adding a deadlock state to the FTS, or the deadlocks in the LTSs should be remedied—again by changing either the behavioural model or the feature model. Hence, based on the detailed feedback obtained by the ambiguity detection algorithm and its implementation presented in [7, 9], the modeller can iteratively improve and check the FTS until the FTS is either unambiguous or ambiguous, but such that it is the FTS as intended by the modeller. We moreover showed that any ambiguous FTS can be turned into an unambiguous FTS by the following transformation:

- (1) remove the dead transitions;
- (2) turn the false optional transitions into must transitions; and
- (3) make explicit the hidden deadlocks (cf. [7, 9] for details).²

Recall that an ambiguous FTS may be due to a mistake of the modeller in defining the feature model, in particular in the case of large feature models with many cross-tree constraints.

Example 3.13. Consider the FTS \mathcal{F} depicted in Figure 4, but now with feature expression $FM_{\mathcal{F}} = f_1 \rightarrow f_2$, i.e. the presence of feature f_1 requires that of f_2 . In this case, the LTS $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda_1}$ has two further a -transitions, viz. loops in states s_0 and s_2 . Thus \mathcal{F} no longer exhibits neither dead transitions nor hidden deadlock states—only the false optional transition $s_1 \xrightarrow{a|f_1} s_2$ remains (cf. Examples 3.9 and 3.12).

²This step must be performed only for those hidden deadlock states that have not yet become explicit deadlock states upon the removal of dead transitions in step (1).

3.3 Modal Transition Systems

MTSs were introduced in [53] to capture the refinement of a partial description into a more detailed one, reflecting increased knowledge on the admissible (but not necessary) behaviour. In [11], MTSs were equipped with a set of variability constraints to compactly model SPL behaviour, whose individual variant behaviour, in the form of an LTS, can be obtained by means of a special-purpose refinement relation, or by an equivalent operational derivation procedure. In [6], it was shown that such MTSs are equally expressive as FTSs. We follow the definitions from [6, 11].

Definition 3.14 (MTS). A *Modal Transition System* (MTS) is a quintuple $\mathcal{M} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\diamond, \delta^\square)$ such that $\delta^\square \subseteq \delta^\diamond$ and $(S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\diamond)$ is an LTS. We distinguish transition relation δ^\diamond expressing *admissible* (may) transitions and transition relation δ^\square expressing *necessary* (must) transitions, whereas the transitions in $\delta^\diamond \setminus \delta^\square$ are called *optional* transitions. We may write $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ for $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\diamond$, $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ for $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\square$ and $s \dashrightarrow s'$ for $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\diamond \setminus \delta^\square$.

Inherited from [6, 11], in the sequel we only consider *coherent* MTSs, i.e. MTSs such that the set of actions labelling necessary transitions and the set of actions labelling optional transitions are disjoint: for all $(p, a, p') \in \delta^\square$ and $(s, b, s') \in \delta^\diamond \setminus \delta^\square$, we have $a \neq b$.

Note that any (may) transition of an MTS is either a must transition or an optional transition. When drawing MTSs, we explicitly depict their must transitions (as solid lines) and their optional transitions (as dashed lines). Again, the notions from Definition 3.2 (path, reachability, deadlock) are carried over in the usual way.

Definition 3.15 (variability constraints). Let $\mathcal{L} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta)$ be an LTS. We define the syntax and semantics of six types of *variability constraints* on the reachability of actions of \mathcal{L} formalised as propositional formulas over Σ interpreted as propositional variables. Let $a_i \in \Sigma$, for all $i \geq 1$, and let $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 3$.

- (1) $b_1 \vee b_2 \vee \dots \vee b_m$, where $b_i \in \{a_i, \neg a_i\}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq m$ (i.e. each literal b_i is either equal to a_i or to its negation): for at least one b_i , $1 \leq i \leq m$, it holds that either
 - $b_i = a_i$ and a_i is reachable in \mathcal{L} , or
 - $b_i = \neg a_i$ and a_i is not reachable in \mathcal{L} ;
- (2) $a_1 \oplus a_2 \oplus \dots \oplus a_m$: precisely one among a_1, \dots, a_m is reachable in \mathcal{L} ;
- (3) $a_1 \uparrow a_2$: at most one among a_1 and a_2 is reachable in \mathcal{L} ;³
- (4) $a_1 \rightarrow a_2$: a_2 is reachable in \mathcal{L} whenever a_1 is reachable in \mathcal{L} ;
- (5) $a_1 \rightarrow (a_2 \oplus a_3 \oplus \dots \oplus a_n)$: precisely one among a_2, \dots, a_n is reachable in \mathcal{L} whenever a_1 is reachable in \mathcal{L} ;
- (6) $a_1 \rightarrow (a_2 \vee a_3 \vee \dots \vee a_n)$: at least one among a_2, \dots, a_n is reachable in \mathcal{L} whenever a_1 is reachable in \mathcal{L} .

Any propositional formula can be converted into an equivalent formula in conjunctive normal form (CNF), i.e. a conjunction of disjunctions of literals (propositional variables or their negation) by applying the laws of distribution, De Morgan's laws, and by removing double negations, possibly requiring exponential time [58]. Hence, variability constraints of type 1 suffice to define all propositional formulae over Σ ; nevertheless, we provide as syntactic sugar the other five types of variability constraints from [6, 11], which stem directly from feature models and are all accepted by VMC.

³Note that \uparrow is the negation of conjunction (a.k.a. *not and*).

Figure 5: MTS v \mathcal{M} modelling a product line of coffee machines

Thus, we may freely use any type of propositional formula over a set of actions because we know that it can always be converted into a set of disjunctive formulae (cf. type 1 from Definition 3.15).

Definition 3.16 (MTS v). An MTS with variability constraints (MTS v) is a sextuple $\mathcal{M} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\diamond, \delta^\square, \Upsilon)$ such that $(S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\diamond, \delta^\square)$ is an MTS and Υ is a set of variability constraints on actions from Σ .

Intuitively, a variant (LTS) is derived from an MTS v by including all must transitions of the MTS v and a subset of its optional transitions. More precisely, the variant LTS has the same set of actions and the same initial state as the MTS v , but a subset of the set of states of the MTS v and a subset of its transitions such that the following four conditions are satisfied: (i) all states of the LTS are reachable from its initial state; (ii) all must transitions of the MTS v are included in the LTS (except those must transitions whose source states are not reachable in the LTS); (iii) for any action a , whenever an a -transition of the MTS v is included in the LTS, then any other (optional) a -transition in the MTS v (from a state that is reachable in the LTS) is also included (i.e. the decision to turn one optional a -transition into a necessary a -transition must be consistently repeated for all other optional a -transitions); (iv) all variability constraints are satisfied. This is formalised next.

Definition 3.17 (variant of MTS v). Let $\mathcal{M} = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\diamond, \delta^\square, \Upsilon)$ be an MTS v . The LTS $\mathcal{L} = (S^\nu, \Sigma, s_0, \delta^\nu)$ is called a *variant* (product) derived from \mathcal{M} whenever $S^\nu \subseteq S$ and $\delta^\nu \subseteq \delta^\diamond$ are such that:

- (1) every $s \in S^\nu$ is reachable in \mathcal{L} ;
- (2) there exists no $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\square \setminus \delta^\nu$ such that $s \in S^\nu$;
- (3) for any $a \in \Sigma$, whenever $(p, a, p') \in \delta^\nu$ for some $p, p' \in S^\nu$, then for all $s, s' \in S^\nu$ such that $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\diamond$ it must be the case that also $(s, a, s') \in \delta^\nu$;
- (4) \mathcal{L} satisfies all variability constraints in Υ .

The set of variants derived from an MTS v \mathcal{M} is denoted by $\text{Its}(\mathcal{M})$.

Note that, by construction, variants do not contain states or actions that were not already present in the MTS v .

Example 3.18. In Figure 5, we depict an MTS v \mathcal{M} modelling the behaviour of the two coffee machines from Example 3.3 as a product line of coffee machines. \mathcal{M} has two must transitions and two optional transitions conditioned by the set of variability constraints $\Upsilon = \{\text{std} \oplus \text{ins}_2\}$. Indeed, the LTSs \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 , depicted in Figure 1, are the only two variants of \mathcal{M} (except that we distinguish ins_1 and ins_2 to make \mathcal{M} coherent).

3.4 Family-Based Model Checking

In [11], a specific kind of family-based model checking was introduced for MTS v . An MTS v is defined to be *live* if all its states are live, where a live state of an MTS v is such that it does not occur as

a deadlock state in any of its variants, effectively resulting in an MTS v in which every path is infinite. It was proved that validity of formulas expressed in $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ is preserved in all variants (cf. [11, Theorem 4]), thus allowing a kind of family-based model checking of MTS v s. It is not difficult to see that this result continues to hold for MTS v s whose every state is either live or a deadlock.

In [7, 9], we noted that any FTS \mathcal{F} can be transformed into an MTS \mathcal{F}_{MTS} by considering its must transitions as necessary transitions, its featured transitions as optional transitions, and all its transitions as admissible, and by removing all feature expressions. And if \mathcal{F} is live, then \mathcal{F}_{MTS} is live, with respect to the FTS's set of variants $\text{Its}(\mathcal{F})$, because it has no hidden deadlocks. Moreover, all transitions of \mathcal{F} whose corresponding (LTS) transitions are mandatorily present in all variants correspond to necessary transitions in \mathcal{F}_{MTS} . This demonstrates that the above result from [11] can be carried over to live FTSs, thus allowing a kind of family-based model checking also on such FTSs for the $v\text{-ACTL}$ fragment $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$. Hence, any formula ϕ of $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ is preserved by live FTSs: given a live FTS \mathcal{F} , whenever ϕ holds for \mathcal{F}_{MTS} , denoted by $\mathcal{F}_{\text{MTS}} \models \phi$, then ϕ holds for all variants $\mathcal{F}|_\lambda \in \text{Its}(\mathcal{F})$, i.e. $\mathcal{F}|_\lambda \models \phi$.

More precisely, if (i) the FTS is live, which is the case if it has no hidden deadlocks (so, unambiguous FTSs are live), and (ii) the property ϕ to be verified is specified in $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$, then ϕ can be verified directly on the FTS (ignoring its feature expressions) and if (iii) ϕ holds, this validity is preserved in all LTSs modelling variant behaviour, i.e. ϕ holds for all variants. If any of these three conditions does not hold, the property needs to be verified with classical (family-based) approaches, like those mentioned in Section 2.

Example 3.19. The MTS \mathcal{M} depicted in Figure 5 (ignoring the set Υ of variability constraints) is exactly the MTS \mathcal{F}_{MTS} obtained from the FTS \mathcal{F} of Example 3.6 according to the above transformation. It is live. In fact, $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ formulas like $\varphi = AG AF_{\text{std} \vee \text{xxl}} \top$ preserve their validity for all variants. When verified on \mathcal{M} , VMC reports that φ is true and that it holds for all variants of \mathcal{M} . Literally, φ expresses that from any state there exists a path that allows to execute *std* or *xxl*, i.e. *it is always possible to eventually obtain a (standard or extra large) coffee*, a prerequisite for any coffee machine.

4 TOOLCHAIN AT WORK

The methodology described in the previous section has been fully automated. With the newly developed front-end tool FTS4VMC, the toolchain constituted by (i) FTS4VMC, (ii) the Python code analyser.py from [8] (implementing the static analysis algorithm from [9], where it was shown to be more efficient than the one presented in [7]) and (iii) VMC, can assist an end user (modeller) in the following steps of the engineering and verification methodology envisioned in Figure 6 (where all green blocks are automated by the toolchain):

- specify or upload an FTS in FTS4VMC or an MTS v in VMC;
- use FTS4VMC to check whether the FTS is ambiguous (by calling analyser.py);
- use FTS4VMC to transform any ambiguous FTS into an unambiguous one (or to remove only some particular kinds of ambiguities detected, by calling disambiguator.py);
- decide whether the FTS is live with FTS4VMC or whether the MTS v is live with VMC;

Figure 6: Engineering and verification methodology

- specify a v-ACTL formula in FTS4VMC or in VMC;
- decide whether the v-ACTL formula is a $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ formula with VMC;
- verify a $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ formula on the FTS (transformed into an MTS by FTS4VMC, by calling `translator.py`) or directly on the MTS_v (transformed into an MTS by VMC) with VMC;
- report validity for all variants of the FTS/ MTS_v in case a $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square$ formula was verified to hold on a live FTS/ MTS_v (a kind of family-based model checking) with VMC;
- verify a $v\text{-ACTLive}^\square/v\text{-ACTL}$ formula on all variants (generated by VMC) of the MTS_v (product-based model checking) with VMC;

The novelties are clearly indicated in the figure: the blue steps and the green steps if applied to FTSs are made possible by FTS4VMC.

The FTS4VMC front-end accepts FTSs in the `.dot` format, a well-known graphical notation supported by the `graphviz` open source graph visualization software (cf. <https://www.graphviz.org>).

Once the FTS has been uploaded and verified to be in the correct format, the user is offered a variety of (analysis) tasks:

Full ambiguities analysis analyzes the FTS for all three types of ambiguities: once done, it outputs an updated version of the FTS with dead transitions highlighted in blue, false optional transitions highlighted in green, and hidden deadlock states highlighted in red (cf. Fig. 7); moreover, it enables the ambiguity removal tasks mentioned below;

Liveness analysis analyzes the FTS for liveness, i.e., whether it has hidden deadlock states but ignoring the detection of dead and false optional transitions;

Stop processing interrupts the current (full ambiguities or liveness) analysis;

Remove all ambiguities performs the next two analyses as a single operation;

Remove false optional transitions replaces the feature expression of each false optional transition of the FTS with True, thus converting these transitions into must transitions; no transitions are added or deleted;

Remove dead transitions and hidden deadlock states deletes unreachable transitions if present, then resolves hidden deadlocks by adding an explicit deadlock state called DEAD and creating special transitions to DEAD starting from every state marked as hidden deadlock with a feature expression equivalent to the negation of the disjunction of every feature expression starting from the hidden deadlock state;

View MTS shows the MTS obtained from the FTS by replacing each must transition (i.e., with feature expression True) into a necessary transition of the MTS and every other transition into an admissible one; updates source and graph (cf. Fig. 9);

Verify property verifies properties expressed in v-ACTL with VMC, once the analysis was completed and the FTS results live, by inserting them in the provided text area;

Show explanation shows the counterexample provided by VMC after having checked the property.

During execution of these tasks, the user is offered different views:

Console displays progress and results of the performed tasks;

Source displays the `.dot` source file of the current FTS;

Graph displays the rendered graph in SVG format, highlighting the feature model and ambiguities;

Summary displays the console output after successful analysis in a more user-friendly way (cf. Fig. 8);

Counterexample graph displays the counterexample obtained upon interaction with VMC rendered as a graph.

Figure 7: FTS with ambiguities reported by FTS4VMC

Figure 8: Full ambiguities analysis reported by FTS4VMC

Figure 9: MTS transformed from the FTS by FTS4VMC

Figure 10: FTS with ambiguities reported by FTS4VMC

Moreover, at any time, the user can download the displayed result (e.g., the FTS in .dot or SVG formal and with or without highlighted ambiguities, the transformed MTS, etc.).

We now show how to apply our methodology to two concrete examples from the literature: the vending machine and minepump from [26, 27], both of which have become de facto FTS benchmarks [5–7, 9, 10, 15, 18, 24, 30, 34–39, 41, 42].

The vending machine (cf. Fig. 7) serves soda or tea, either for free or upon payment, in which case a compartment is opened for the customer to take the beverage before it is closed again. Its feature model is represented by the feature expression $s \vee t$ over the features $\{f, c, s, t\}$, thus resulting in 12 configurations. The FTS of the vending machine contains 9 states and 13 transitions.

Figures 7 and 8 show the result of the full ambiguities analysis reported by FTS4VMC, while Figure 9 shows the MTS obtained by transforming the FTS.

As mentioned in [7, 9], example v-CTL formulas of branching-time properties of the vending machine FTS that can be verified in a kind of family-based manner with FTS4VMC on the corresponding MTS include the following:

- (1) $[pay] AF_{take \vee cancel} \top$: whenever a customer pays, eventually (s)he will also either take a beverage or cancel payment;⁴
- (2) $AG AF_{pay \vee free} \top$: infinitely often, a customer will either pay or opt for a free beverage.

⁴Abusing notation, this concerns execution of transition (8, take, 9), not of (7, take, 1).

The minepump has to keep a mine safe from flooding by pumping water from a shaft while avoiding a methane explosion. The system FTS models the logic of a configurable controller, which interacts with an environment, to operate a water pump based on water and methane level sensors modelled by further FTSs. It contains 25 states and 41 transitions.⁵ The complete minepump model is the parallel composition of five FTSs, for a total of 418 states and 1255 transitions. The feature model of the minepump can be represented by the formula $\phi = (c \leftrightarrow (ct \vee cp)) \wedge l$ over the feature set $F = \{c, ct, cp, m, l, ll, ln, lh\}$, thus resulting in 64 configurations.

Figure 10 shows the result of the full ambiguities analysis by FTS4VMC. The system FTS contains numerous false optional transitions and a hidden deadlock state: s_{20} is reachable in all variants upon execution of 2 must transitions (actually, the second one is false optional transition ($s_7, levelMsg, l, s_{20}$)) but it is a deadlock state in all 8 variants that lack a feature from the subset $\{ll, ln, lh\}$. FTS4VMC can remove this deadlock state by adding an explicit deadlock state DEAD and a transition ($s_{20}, \dagger, \neg ll \wedge \neg ln \wedge \neg lh, DEAD$). However, a deadlock often indicates a modelling error, either in the feature model or in the behavioural model. In fact, the solution opted for in [10, 26, 38, 39, 41]⁶ is to modify the FTS by adding transitions from state s_{20} to initial state s_6 to cover the cases in which features from the subset $\{ll, ln, lh\}$ are missing, viz. ($s_{20}, highLevel, \neg lh, s_6$), ($s_{20}, lowLevel, \neg ll, s_6$), and ($s_{20}, normalLevel, \neg ln, s_6$).

⁵Transitions with more than one label abbreviate a set of transitions, viz. one per label.

⁶These papers are based on the high-level specification of the minepump in fPromela as distributed with SNIP and ProVeLines or their translations for VMC or mCRL2 [17, 31].

Figure 11: LTL verification methodology

As mentioned in [7, 9], example v-ACTL formulas of branching-time properties of the minepump FTS that can be verified in a kind of family-based manner with FTS4VMC on the corresponding MTS include the following (where (2) is a variant):⁷

- (1) $AG [palarmMsg] \neg E [\top \neg_{setMethaneStop} U_{palarmMsg} \top]$: it is not possible that two methane `palarmMsg` messages occur without a `setMethaneStop` in between;
- (2) $AG \neg (level \wedge EX_{levelMsg} \top)$: a water `levelMsg` message cannot be received if the water level is already known.

5 FUTURE WORK

In [7], we considered only branching-time properties. However, in [9] we also considered linear-time properties and showed that a live FTS also enjoys the property that all valid linear-time LTL formulas are preserved by all its variants. This can be seen as follows. A path in an LTS is said to be *maximal* if it cannot be extended further, i.e. it is infinite or it ends in a deadlock state. Model checking LTL formulas on an LTS reduces to analysing its maximal paths: an LTL formula is valid if it holds for all maximal paths. These notions trivially carry over to FTSs by ignoring their feature expressions. Clearly, if an FTS is live, i.e. it has no hidden deadlocks, then the set of maximal paths of any variant (LTS) is a subset of the set of maximal paths of the FTS. Hence, the following result holds. Any formula ϕ of LTL is preserved by live FTSs: given a live FTS \mathcal{F} , whenever ϕ holds for \mathcal{F}_{LTS} , denoted by $\mathcal{F}_{LTS} \models \phi$, then ϕ holds for all variants $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda} \in \text{Its}(\mathcal{F})$, i.e. $\mathcal{F}|_{\lambda} \models \phi$. The verification methodology depicted in Figure 11 can thus be envisioned.

As mentioned in [9], example formulas of linear-time properties of the vending machine FTS that can be verified in a kind of family-based manner with tools like SPIN [49] (<http://spinroot.com>) include the following:⁸

- (1) $\Box (selected \Rightarrow \Diamond served)$: after a beverage is selected, the vending machine will always eventually serve a beverage;
- (2) $\Box (served \Rightarrow \Diamond taken)$: after a beverage is served, a customer will always eventually take the beverage.

⁷In [22, 23], the states of the FTSs constituting the complete minepump model are labelled with atomic propositions. In particular, state s_{20} of the system FTS (cf. Fig. 10) is labelled with the proposition *level*.

⁸In [26, 27], the states of an FTS are labelled with atomic propositions, omitted in figures to avoid clutter. For LTL model checking with SPIN, we assume that states 5 and 6 of the FTS (cf. Fig. 7) are labelled with the proposition *selected*, state 7 with the proposition *served*, and states 1 and 9 with the proposition *taken*.

As mentioned in [9], example formulas of linear-time properties of the minepump FTS that can be verified in a kind of family-based manner with tools like SPIN include the following:⁹

- (1) $((\Box \Diamond readCommand) \wedge (\Box \Diamond readAlarm) \wedge (\Box \Diamond readLevel)) \Rightarrow (\neg \Diamond \Box (\neg pumpOn \wedge \neg methane \wedge highWater))$: if the controller fairly receives each of the three message types, then the pump is never indefinitely off when the water is high.
- (2) $\Box ((\neg pumpOn \wedge lowWater \wedge \Diamond highWater) \Rightarrow ((\neg pumpOn) U highWater))$: when the pump is off and the water is low, the pump will only start once the water is high again.

The latter properties (1) and (2) are precisely the properties #34 and #41, respectively, as verified with both SNIP and SPIN in [26].

6 CONCLUSION

We presented FTS4VMC, developed specifically as a front-end for VMC with a user-friendly GUI. It has code to upload and download files, handle users' session data, render graph visualization and HTML output, and communicate with VMC. It also contains Python code: `analyser.py` from [8], implementing the ambiguities analysis; `disambiguator.py`, implementing the ambiguities removal; `graph.py`, implementing the FTS/MTS graph rendering; `translator.py`, implementing the transformation of an FTS into an MTS; `vmc_controller.py`, handling the property verification with VMC; and `process_manager.py`, handling multiprocessing required for real-time output during the analysis process. The resulting toolchain allows a modeller to analyse an FTS for ambiguities, remove them, and perform an efficient kind of family-based model checking of specific branching-time properties on the resulting FTS.

The results, mentioned in this paper, that form the basis of the verification methodologies depicted in Figures 6 and 11 indicate specific cases in which verification of live FTSs reduces to verification (with a linear complexity) of corresponding MTSs and LTSs that are obtained straightforwardly by ignoring the feature expressions (and distinguishing necessary and optional transitions in case of MTSs). However, if either (i) the property to be verified is not a v-ACTL[□] or LTL formula, or (ii) the result of the verification is false, then the formula needs to be verified with a classical family-based model checking tool or by means of product-based model checking.

⁹In the fPromela specification of the complete minepump model, `pumpOn` and `methane` are Booleans that are set to true when the pump is turned on or methane is detected, respectively, whereas the remaining variables are macros (e.g., `readCommand` defines that the minepump FTS (cf. Fig. 10) has received a `commandMsg`, while `highWater` defines that the FTS has received a `levelMsg` stating that the water level is high).

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